

Unheard voice of The Nomadic Tribes

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Abstract:

There is an attempt to reveal the similar problems of the narratives *The Branded* by Laxman Gaikwad, *An Outsider* by Laxman Mane and *Against All Odds* by Kishor Kale. The communities mentioned in these narratives come from the same background of lower caste. Nomadic tribes such as Uchaly, Kaikadi and Kolhati are ill-treated by the dominant people. The women of these communities are given oppressed doubly by the patriarchy and upper class society. The people of these communities are frequently gone through torture and suffering. They faced the problem of caste and untouchability. The narrators are inspired by Dr B. R. Ambedkar and wanted to liberate their communities from the age old habits and customs. The narrators tried to express their agonies and pains of their communities. They also revealed the problems of their communities such as poverty, illiteracy, hunger, starvation, humiliation, superstitions, jatpanchayat and subordinate position of their women.

Rational of The Study: The narratives under study explain soci, economic and religious ethos of nomadic tribes. The study of these works inspire and motivates reader to establish an egalitarian and cosmopolitan human society based on the principles of equality, liberty, fraternity and justice. The narratives are the live experience of nomadic tribes and their struggle for existence.

Objectives of the Study: The Research paper aims at bringing our socio, cultural, economical and religious perspectives of the communities. The study investigates the causes and consequences of degradation of the communities. It also attempt to surface the problems poverty, hunger, illiteracy, superstitions, humiliation, jatpanchayat etc.

Methodology: The present study has uses MLA Handbook for Writers of Research Paper (Nicholls, 7th edition) as the basis for its style manual. The entire technical format, references entries are used according to the guidelines of MLA. Analytical, descriptive and comparative methods are followed while interpreting the narratives. The proposed study does not require any practical or field work. The basic text and the reference books have been referred as primary data and secondary data.

Conclusion: The problems of poverty, illiteracy, starvation, blind faith, rituals, humiliation, subjugation of women ,jatpanchayat are the major issues raised through these narratives. The nomadic tribes such as Uchaya, Kaikadi and Kolhati are given brutal treatment by the dominant class. The communities are deprived from their fundamental rights.

Suggestion: As a human being Communities like Kaikadi, Uchalya and Kolhati are to given educational rights to come out from their age old

habits. They are not stable because of their basic need of food shelter and clothes. So the communities are to be provided work to fulfill their hunger. The claim of thief on these communities is be wiped away to bring them in main stream of society. The government should look into the problem of these people and make the policies for the welfare of these underprivileged communities. The selected narratives such as *The Branded* by Laxman Gaikwad, *An Outsider* by Laxman Mane and *Against All Odds* by Kishor Kale are the life stories of victimized Nomadic tribes such as *Uchaly*, *Kaikadi* and *Kolhati*. These tribes are underestimated and brought to the inhuman level of beasts and brutes by the main stream society. The above writers are being known as Dalit writers come from the same marginal classes. They are the representative of their own communities. They are excluded from the opportunities and benefits of Indian Independence. These writers narrated their own experiences of miseries and suffering in the so called established society. The selected autobiographies are the sincere attempt to bring out the oppressed voice. The writers were the victim of the main stream society. These works are live experiences of subjugation and humiliation of the oppressed classes. They have narrated painful life of their own community through their own journey of life. These writers have come from the same backgrounds with their similar problems. They have revealed their way of life from their childhood to adult age. The socio-cultural aspects of the oppressed classes are minutely observed in the selected autobiographies. The poor economical conditions of these communities are equally brought into our notice through these works. They

were victimized on various grounds dominated by so called established people. These writers are inspired their own voice against established and dominant class who made their life miserable and critical to live dignified life.

Mane, Gaikwad and Kale are inspired by the modern dramatic values such as equality, liberty, fraternity and justice in their way of life. They are also motivated and accelerated the feeling of liberation and freedom by the thoughts of Dr. B.R. Ambedkar and the prominent dalit writers. J. M. Waghmare writes about the effect of dalit writing upon the marginalized groups: "Emergence of Dalit literature has a great historical significance in India. It is generic in the sense that all other marginalized and oppressed groups of people are under its sway and sweep. It has struck a keynote awakening their consciousness for forging their identities. It has given ample inspiration and insight to the writers emerging from the tribal and nomadic communities. Writers like Laxman Mane, Laxman Gaikwad, Kishor Kale and Waharu Sonvane are a few outstanding examples."¹ These enlightened groups tried to disclose the pain, agonies and raised the voice of socio-cultural transformation of the underprivileged groups.

The similar problems are raised by these writers of their own community in the present work. The caste factor was one of the major problems in the life of these deprived classes. Poverty is one more additional problem is observed in the life of these depressed classes in their every path of life. Nobody of these communities is escaped from the clutches of poverty. Hunger is also one of the common problems narrated by these writers in their work. They struggled for their bread and butter from their childhood. These deprived communities are collapsed due to the problems of superstition, ignorance, illiteracy, addiction and debt. They had number of problem due to their own caste while getting education. *Jatpanchayat* is also played important role in these oppressed communities narrated in these autobiographies. It interfered in the common life of these oppressed classes. The inhuman treatment lodged upon these oppressed classes was the sorrow of these writers. The helpless and pathetic condition of these subjugated classes was major aspect of these writers. The narrators have observed the miserable and painful condition of oppressed classes under the influence of various factors. They have also brought into our

notice the dominant and dignified life of handful of people in mainstream society. There are series of events of humiliation, exploitation and deprivation of these lower classes. The struggles of the parents of these writers are notable and full of hard work. The experiences of ghosts, sacrificing goats, fair, and festivals are commonly observed in these works. The several childhood accounts are equally narrated in these autobiographies. The struggle for education was common experiences narrated by these writers. They had gone to school without uniform and books in their dire poverty.

The concerned writers are lived with number of problems in their communities. They had come across similar problems narrated through their own autobiographies. These writers were around thirty while writing these autobiographies. These works are literary incomplete but meaningful and realistic one. They insisted that the works should be analyzed sociological point of view instead of literary one. In this regard Gaikwad himself asserted, "Let there be a sociological evaluation rather than a literary one of this work. This is my humble expectation."² The attempt of these narrators is same to revolts against oppression and exploitation and demands social and economic justice. The text are based on moral values and welfare of the down-trodden classes. The thematic concern is humanistic which is closely associated with the hopes for freedom of a group of people who are victims of social, economic, and cultural inequality. The narrators believe that the narratives should be analyzed from a sociological perspective focused on social and moral values. The present writing looks at reality with open eyes. It views every aspect of life objectively. The exploitation and atrocities in the deprived classes are commonly narrated. These writers are not accepted social values of an exploiting system. Any literature should be associated with the hopes for freedom of group of people who are victims of social, economical and cultural inequality. Arjun Dangale urged for sociological evaluation of Dalit literature. "Studying Dalit literature or the role of this literature from only a literary or an academic point of view fails to present a complete perspective in assessing it. Dalit literature must be assessed in the sociological framework."³ The literary manifestation of this social awareness is essential part of Dalit literature

Language used in the present works is against the conventional norms of autobiography.

These writers avoided the use of standardized Marathi words, phrases and ideas. The works are found in their own native and natural language. There is no use of artificiality and farfetched ideas. The present dalit autobiographies have broken the rule of traditional writings. In this regard R.S.Jain rightly put "Person and personality, beginning and development, character and characterization, sophisticated mixture of fact and fiction, well-knit plot of events and eventualities of the Marathi literature were replaced by a different set of persons, characters, events, motifs and plots."⁴ These works resembled rawness and rusticity of words. There is no use of technique to attract, impress or influence people. There was no well thought plan to attract sympathy and pity of others. The works seem to be honest sincere and natural. These works are lack in style and technique but thoughtful and meaningful. The use of language is simple, honest and natural. They have succeeded in their narrative technique through the simple and straight forward method. The writers are faithful in their presentation. Lxaman Mane, Laxman Gaikwad and Kishor Kale tried to write like accomplished writers.

The view of life conveyed in these autobiographies is different from the established writing. We would come into contact with new world, a new society. The languages of these narratives are distinct one of the reality. The language employed is the spoken language of these deprived and subjugated classes. The languages of these narratives are recognized an uncultured and barbaric one. The idioms and phrases are supposed uncultivated and savage. The narrators used quarter language rather than the standard one. The present autobiographies have rejected the standard language. The educated and cultured people blamed these narratives for its abusive language and rusticity. But the oppressed enlightened writer preferred native language rather the standard one. Sharan kumar rightly speaks regarding the uniqueness of mother tongue while narrating the dalit experiences: "In fact, standard language does not include all the words of Dalit dialect. Besides, the ability to voice one's experience in one's mother tongue gives greater sharpness to the expression."⁵ The present autobiographies have referred the idioms and phrases which are appropriate for revealing the inner world of the oppressed classes. The distinctive use of language in the present autobiographies contributes in Marathi language and literature as well.

The present autobiographies in Marathi have been translated into English enriching not only Indian literatures in English but also the world literature of the marginal groups. The languages of these autobiographies are the languages of oppressed classes such as *Uchalya*, *Kaikadi* and *Kolhati* community. Sometime it is felt difficult to understand. But at the same time, they are contributing in the vocabulary of Marathi language. The treatments of social values are important in compare to literary values in these autobiographies.

The present autobiographies have narrated the culture of these communities. Thieving was the main business of the Pathrut community. The fair and festivals are the essential part of these communities. The marriage system of these communities and their Jatpanchayat were special of these communities. The age old method of 'Chira Utarna' was common practice in Kolhati community. The different religious places and gods are the special attraction of these autobiographies. The present works are full of cultural experiences of these nomadic communities. There are many incidents in these autobiographies help us to understand the culture and customs of these people. It also makes us to realize the fact in these deprived nomadic communities.

Most of the Dalit autobiographies are the projection of rural and urban culture. The present works narrated the rural and urban life of these communities. These writers initially came from rural and then entered in urban life. In the result the present work recorded both the experiences of rural and urban life of these communities. Gaikwad narrates his journey of life from his childhood to a social worker. In his course of work he touched rural and urban life. The incidents and experiences presented in *An Outsider* by Mane are from rural and urban. *Against All Odds* is also perfect projection of rural and urban life. Mixture of rural and urban culture is a notable thing of these works. The half of the life of these writers is developed in rural part. They entered in the city life after thirty for different social activities. After the completion of their basic education, they involved in social work to motivate their community

The problem of hunger and poverty is commonly observed in the present autobiographies. The communities mentioned in the present work have not fulfilled their basic

needs. To complete their hunger was the major barriers in their way of life. They are struggling for their bread and butter from their very beginning of life. They are deprived of their fundamental needs such as food, shelter and clothes. They never got sufficient food in their way of life. Most of the time they lived on left over food from the villages nearby. Sometimes the entire family of ten to fifteen people went without food for days together. Laxman Gaikwad roasted rats, pigs and ate to full fill his stomach. They ate leftover, stale food in the marriages for days together Dr. Lulekar rightly narrated the picture of Pathrut community: "Stealing for stomach, punishment for stealing, stealing after completion of punishment. Such was the rotation of Pathruts life." ⁶There are an innumerable records of hunger observed with these deprived classes such as Pathrut, Kaikadi and Kolhati. They are always followed poverty and hunger and struggled for their existence. The picture of poverty and hunger is frequently portrayed in the present works. These writers are the real victim of poverty in their community portrayed through these memoirs. The writers were victimized under various problems raised in the present work.

The selected Dalit memoirs such as *An Outsider*, *The Branded* and *Against All Odds* attempts to realize the world of downtrodden and their unheard agonies and painful life in the presence of so called established Hindus. The present writers were suffered due to their lower castes. Laxman Mane, Laxman Gaikwad, Kishor Kale could not get residences even when they were educated and qualified. They were not employed in the government job simply because of their birth in lower castes. All these writers had to lie about their castes in the society. These writers faced all sort of torture and humiliation at their childhood while acquiring formal education. School children, their teachers discouraged these writers by attacking on their low castes. Teachers reserved a secluded corner of a classroom for them. Other children of the villages avoided their company. Yet these autobiographers surpassed every kind of hurdles and difficulties and became successful. Thus education of these writers solved their age old problems in their life. .

Superstition and blind belief were the part and parcel of these nomadic tribes. Already the people of these communities were far away from education. The lives of these communities were

completely influenced by the traditions and customs. The writers of these communities provided innumerable account of blind beliefs and superstitions through their autobiographies. Waman Nimbalkar writes about the beliefs of these communities as "There are many incidents in the autobiography that highlight ignorance, superstitions, faith in miracles, rampant in the community"⁷

The people of lower communities believed in blind belief and miracles in their every sphere of life. Once, Gaikwad was admitted to school by his father Martand. Suddenly, the children of the village were suffered from loose motion and vomiting. The village people blamed Martand for admitting his son to school. They linked the relation between the incident of schooling of Gaikwad and loose motion of the children of the village. Actually it was blind belief of the village people. Gaikwad put an account of pass which is received from village Patil for their community. The people of Pathrut worshiped their pass as god and the blade as Laxmi in their family. Gaikwad says whenever his grandfather, grandmother and others in his family set out on a thieving mission, they bought a cock and sacrificed it to the blade, sprinkled some drops of its blood on the blade and the pass. Gaikwad noticed his father's belief: "Once my father had told me that if one sat continuously for a month between a *rui* and a berry tree to relieve oneself, and then buried a rupee between these trees located in a cemetery, one would always be left with a rupee in his purpose, whatever amount one might spend. Moreover such a person understood the language of bird."⁸ Laxman Mane also narrated the belief and ritual of his own community. It was routine of their community to wander from one place to another with their caravan. Once, Laxman's father approached a new place where he was intended to settle with his family. Mane narrated the belief of his father in God by joining his palms and prayed as "Bless us with good luck." He took a pinch of vermilion from inside the basket of the idols and threw it on the ground. Kaikadi community was influenced so much with their blind belief and rituals in their every path of life. They never forgot their gods and deities. Limbale made the record of Kaikadi community in the words: "The exploitation and the predicament of Kaikadi community is based on the dominant factor such as superstitious belief and faith in god."⁹

We have also an account of beliefs in Kolhati community. Once Nana, a supposed husband of Shanta picked up the images of the gods from her little Puja placed and threw them at her, when she was menstruating. Shanta did not touch anything or anyone in the house and touching her gods was blasphemous. It was an orthodox Indian belief that women were unclean when they menstruate, and so far four days they did not touch anything in the house. Once Shanta rushed into the sitting room and saw the cobra with its raised head and hood. Kishor narrates: "The cobra is symbolic of lord Shiva, who wears one round his neck, and Monday is Shiva's day. Shanta fasted and prayed to Shiva every Monday."¹⁰ Thus the selected autobiographies are full of blind belief and faith in god.

The communities narrated in these autobiographies are marginalized and deprived one. The selected writers are influenced by the thoughts of Dr.B.R.Ambedkar and modern values. In the result, they first time challenged the exploitation of their community through their narratives in the history of Dalit literature .These autobiographies are the records of exploitation, humiliation and harassment of these communities such as *Kaikadi*, *Pathrut* and *Kolhati*. Pains, sufferings, sorrows and miseries of these communities are the major aspect of these autobiographies. The writers have tried to project realistic account of their own community through these autobiographies. The languages of these autobiographies are against the traditional rule of Marathi language. These autobiographies are written in the languages of these communities. The use of language is the special feature of these works. The selected works are literary incomplete. But sociological point of view they are sound and authentic one. The problems of these communities are projected social point of view. Moral values are the basement of these autobiographies.

The writers projected the journey of their life from their childhood to adult age. The experiences of these writers were full of struggle and exploitation. They moved towards an act social work after their education and settlement in life. They contributed in their own community through their different social work. The present autobiographies raised voice against caste, untouchability, inherent occupation, women torture, poverty, hunger and so many unsolved problems of these nomadic tribes. The communities mentioned in the present

autobiographies lived a life of poverty, starvation, ignorance, insults, injustice, atrocities – practices totally against humanity and democratic values. The journey of these writers is leading towards liberation of their own community. They are trying to liberate their own community from different hurdles and difficulties.

The world is narrated by these writers never became the subject of established writers earlier. The present autobiographies are written against the so called established culture and tradition. They have broken every norms of prevailed writing and established their own identity. The attempt of transformation and emancipation of these deprived classes from the domination of established age old Hindu culture attracts our attention and made us to sympathies towards these oppressed classes. Definitely, somewhere we are approaching towards the goal of these narrators behind the writing of the autobiographies. It can be realized with the statement of Gaikwad: "Hence this urge to write to awaken this bourgeois society to the sorrow and plight of my unfortunate community."¹¹

References

1. Aston,N.M. 2001 *Literature of Marginality : Dalit Literature and African American Literatur* , New Delhi: Prestige Book, 22
2. Gaikwad, Laxman. 1998. *The Branded*. Translated by P A Kolharkar. New Delhi: Sahitya Akademi, IX
3. Dangle, Arjun. 1992. *Poisoned Bread. Translation from Modern Marathi Dalit Literature*. New Delhi: Orient Blackswan,237
4. Jain, R S. 2006. *Dalit Autobiography*. Ahmednager: Ritu Prakshan,07
5. Limbale, Sharankumar. 2004. *Towards an Aesthetic of Dalit Literature*. Translated from the Marathi by Alok Mukharjee. New Delhi: Orient Blackswan,34
6. Dr. Lulekar, Pralhad. 2000. *Vednancha Pradesh*. Aurangabad: Kailash Publication,186
7. Nimbalkar, Waman. 2006. *Dalit Literature: Nature and Role*. Translated from Marathi by Vandana Pathak & Nimsarkar. Nagpur: Prabodhan Prakashan,143
8. Gaikwad, Laxman. 1998. *The Branded*. Translated by P A Kolharkar. New Delhi: Sahitya Akademi,85
9. Nimbalkar, Waman. *Dalit Literature: Nature and Role*. Translated from Marathi by

- Vandana Pathak & Nimsarkar. Nagpur:
Prabodhan Prakashan,140
10. Kale, Kishor Shantabai. 2000. *Against All Odds*. Translated by Sandhya Pandey. New Delhi: Penguin,135
 11. Dangle, Arjun. 1992. *Poisoned Bread. Translation from Modern Marathi Dalit Literature*. New Delhi: Orient Blackswan, 269